

ANALYSIS OF FAMILY BUSINESS IN INTERNATIONAL PRACTICE

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Abstract. This article examines the approaches of various scientists on the nature, importance and specific characteristics of family business. The index of countries on family business, family companies, the current situation of family business in Finland is analyzed as an example of the international practice of family business. Relevant conclusions were formed based on the conducted studies.

Key words: family business, family enterprises, family business index for countries, family traditions, life cycle of family business.

INTRODUCTION. In the modern economy, one can witness various organizational and legal forms of doing business. The existence of such diversity helps to organize business efficiently by choosing a convenient organizational and legal form of doing business. Today, not only in our country, but also in international practice, attention is being paid to family business. We can see from the international practice that some family companies, even a number of developing countries, receive an annual income exceeding the GDP. A number of measures are being implemented in our country to effectively organize family business and turn it into one of the most profitable forms of business, but there are still problems that need to be solved. In particular, problems such as the fact that all the legal and regulatory documents adopted for running family business do not work effectively in practice, insufficient favorable conditions for the activities of family entrepreneurs, obstacles in the export of products produced by family entrepreneurs are among these problems. The existence of such shortcomings and problems and the need to eliminate them show the relevance of studying the

international practice of family business. Therefore, below we will analyze the international practice of family business.

LITERATURE REVIEW. Research on family business has been carried out by various economists around the world. In particular, a group of foreign scholars stated that "family business is a dominant form of business globally, especially in Asia, but compared to the current theories in Western countries that are used to generalize family business, the conceptual study of factors influencing the strategic behavior of family businesses in Asia is lacking. and empirical studies are significantly scarce. More than 80% of enterprises worth US\$1 billion in Southeast Asia are family businesses or conglomerates, and family businesses account for up to 85% of national GDP in ten countries in the region" [1].

Other researchers have focused on the unique characteristics of family businesses. In particular, "as a result of the initial practical experience of entrepreneurs in family business, it can be remembered by the informal dependence of the network and the interference of family members, which can prevent the entrepreneurial family business from acquiring new knowledge and making scientific research investments. In theory, there is a priority in green innovation in restructured family companies" [2].

Researchers also paid attention to the emergence of family business. "Family business is one of the oldest and basic forms of business organization. In today's competitive environment, the growth and survival of family businesses depends on a number of factors. In particular, these include the formation, expansion or reconfiguration of organizational capabilities in response to a rapidly changing environment. The existence of a single management for the organization and implementation of the directions of action of family members plays an important role in solving business problems and realizing goals" [3].

"A business in which common ownership and control is exercised by a family and at least two or more family members participate in the management of

the business is considered a family business and is of great importance worldwide. They make up more than 70% of all businesses, create an average of 60% of jobs, and contribute an average of 67% to world gross domestic product (GDP)” [4].

Other researchers have compared family businesses with state-owned enterprises. "The unique ownership structure of family businesses allows them to establish long-term activities that are often lacking in traditional state-owned companies. They give up excess income during periods of financial stability to increase their chances of survival during periods of financial distress. A CEO of a family-run company may have financial incentives similar to those of CEOs of non-family companies, but the family commitment he or she feels leads to very different strategic choices. Leaders of family businesses often invest in a 10- or 20-year horizon and focus on what they can do now for the next generation” [5].

According to P. Pounder, "the general definition of a family company is that the family has sufficient equity capital to exercise control over the strategy and participate in top management positions. Family traditions and their legacy are very important in this business and the younger generations tend to stay true to their family's way of doing business. This is important because family heritage and traditions are preserved and play an important role in decision-making” [6].

We can witness that extensive research has been conducted on family business in Uzbekistan. "A family enterprise is a small business entity established by its participants for the production and sale of goods on a voluntary basis, on the basis of shared or common property of the participants, as well as on the basis of the property of each of the participants. The activity of a family business is based on the personal work of its participants. A family business operates only as a legal entity" [7].

The researchers led by Sh. Kuvandikov stated that "the family business support system is implemented in several directions and is a complex process that requires specific approaches. In-depth study and analysis of such complex

processes now requires the need to discover non-traditional methodological concepts, principles of a different approach to the problem. The principles of a synergetic approach to solving problems as a new field of science are of great importance in the research of these processes, creating the need to widely use its methodological capabilities. The use of synergetic methods in the field of entrepreneurship greatly contributes to the development of its methodology, and proves the ideas about the synergetic nature of the process of organizing and conducting business activities, that is, the nature of self-organization" [8].

Agreeing with the opinion of the above researchers, we can say that the development of family business on the scale of our country and the development of effective organizational mechanisms are of great importance in the development of our country's economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. This article uses the method of comparison by comparing the indicators of different countries and companies during the analysis of the international practice of family business. Analysis, synthesis and scientific abstraction were carried out by performing various analyses.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS. In recent years, not only researchers, but also large organizations have been conducting research on the development of family business around the world. Especially during the pandemic, the importance of research on maintaining and effectively organizing family business has increased. In particular, every year Family Enterprise USA (FEUSA) conducts a survey of family businesses to learn what issues affect family businesses. "In the latest FEUSA survey, conducted from January 6, 2022 to March 31, 2022, 172 US family business leaders representing 11 US states expressed their views on the challenges faced by companies in the wake of the coronavirus outbreak, as well as the progress of family. In particular, in 2022, 58% of family business subjects saw a decrease in income, and 42% increased it.

Business owners cited industry conditions, economic uncertainty, government regulations, finding skilled workers and the Covid-19 pandemic as the biggest factors affecting changes in revenue, success and growth. In order to effectively manage family businesses during the pandemic, 27 percent of them retained employees, while 18 percent of companies protected employees by working remotely. 16% of companies have cut costs and 5% have changed their product or service line. 8% of companies have reduced their employees and 1% of companies have closed their business" [9].

Table 1

Family Business Country Index [10]

Country name	2022 results	The place occupied by 2022	2020 results	The place occupied by 2020
USA	64,19	1	64,15	2
Great Britain	61,33	2	65,93	1
Netherlands	61,00	3	63,90	3
Canada	60,49	4	62,76	4
Denmark	60,42	5	59,36	7
Switzerland	60,25	6	61,55	5
Sweden	58,63	7	60,54	6
Ireland	58,48	8	57,53	9
Austria	57,58	9	56,61	10
Finland	57,13	10	58,40	8
Czech	56,38	11	55,92	11
Poland	51,97	12	53,39	12
Belgium	51,94	13	51,89	13
Hungary	50,83	14	50,39	15
Portugal	50,11	15	48,73	16
Slovakia	49,65	16	48,63	17
Germany	49,36	17	50,97	14

France	46,17	18	45,84	20
Spain	45,25	19	45,92	19
Japan	45,18	20	47,78	18
Italy	37,88	21	37,76	21

The index of countries on family business focuses on the activities of companies in which the control package of shares belongs to the same family, regardless of the degree of participation of family members in the organizational and legal form of the company and management functions. This index evaluates family business in six different areas: tax; labor costs, productivity and human capital; regulation; financing; infrastructure and institutions and energy. As of the 2020 report, the Country Index for Family Businesses covers 21 countries. The ranking for each country is calculated in a multi-step process. Relevant indicators are determined for each of the six areas defined above. The score values for these indicators are summed to develop a score for each area. The six directions are then summed to create a total index value. Below is the index of countries for family business (Table 1).

If we pay attention to the data in Table 1, the United States is the leader in this index by the end of 2022, while the United Kingdom was the leader in 2020. According to the results of 2022, the top 10 countries in this index, in addition to the United States, included Great Britain, the Netherlands, Canada, Denmark, Switzerland, Sweden, Ireland, Austria, and Finland. In general, in the 21 countries listed in Table 1, family business is more popular than in other countries and favorable conditions have been created for it.

Today, there are many well-known family-run companies in international practice. In Table 2 below, we analyze the world's top 25 family companies in 2022.

In Table 2, among the companies owned by families, the leadership belongs to Walmart. Also, famous companies such as Volkswagen, Berkshire Hathaway,

Ford, BMW, Koch Industries, Dell Technologies, LG Electronics were established on the basis of family business. If we focus on the indicators, Walmart will make almost 560 billion in 2021. INEOS Group Holdings S.A. ranked 25th if it saw revenue in the amount of US dollars. and the company 61 billion. Earned in the amount of US dollars. Also, along with companies from developed countries such as the USA, Germany, France, companies from rapidly developing countries such as China, India, South Korea, and Luxembourg were included in this list. If we focus on the families that own the listed companies, we can see that these companies are owned and managed by world-famous families such as Walton, Porsche, Buffet, Schwarz, Ford, Tata, Koch, Dell. If we look at the life cycle of these companies, we can find companies with a history of one and a half centuries, starting from 25 years old. From this we can see that today in developed and developing countries around the world, family business among other types of business has become a large type of business and shows special features of family business finance.

Table 2

Analysis of the world's top 25 family companies in 2022 [11]

№	Company name	Name of the owning family	Share of the owning family	Date of establishment	Country	Annual revenue (million USD)
1.	Walmart Inc.	Walton	47,1	1962	USA	559 151,0
2.	Volkswagen AG	Porsche and Piech	53,3	1937	Germany	284 544,0
3.	Berkshire Hathaway Inc.	Buffet	37,3	1955	USA	276 094,0
4.	Schwarz Group	Schwarz	100,0	1930	Germany	142 499,7
5.	Ford Motor Co.	Ford	40,0	1903	USA	136 341,0
6.	Gunvor Group Ltd.	Tornqvist	88,4	2000	Switzerland	135 000,0
7.	Cargill Inc.	Cargill, MacMillan	90,0	1865	USA	134 426,0
8.	ALDI Group	Albrecht	100,0	1948	Germany	133 113,1
9.	Tata Sons Private Ltd.	Tata	66,0	1868	India	128 000,0

10.	Bayerische Motoren Werke AG (BMW)	Quandt, Klatten	46,7	1916	Germany	126 508,6
11.	Comcast Corp.	Roberts	33,3	1963	USA	116 385,0
12.	Koch Industries Inc.	Koch	100,0	1940	USA	115 000,0
13.	Dell Technologies Inc.	Dell	72,0	1984	USA	86 670,0
14.	SK Group	Chey	32,7	1953	South Korea	82 545,6
15.	Country Garden Holdings Co. Ltd.	Yang	62,0	1992	China	82 338,6
16.	ArcelorMittal S.A.	Mittal	37,6	1976	Luxembourg	76 571,0
17.	LVMH Moet Hennessy	Arnault	47,4	1987	France	73 029,7
18.	Roche Holding AG	Hoffmann, Oeri, Duschmale	45,0	1896	Switzerland	72 234,8
19.	China Evergrande Group	Hui	65,8	1996	China	71 751,6
20.	Pacific Construction Group Co. Ltd.	Yan	100,0	1995	China	64 037,7
21.	Reliance Industries Ltd.	Ambani	47,4	1973	India	63 822,2
22.	JBS S.A.	Batista	43,2	1953	Brazil	62 942,3
23.	LG Electronics Inc.	Koo	30,8	1947	South Korea	62 730,2
24.	A.P. Muller-Maersk	Muller, Maersk, Mc-Kinney Uggla	69,9	1904	Denmark	61 787,0
25.	INEOS Group Holdings S.A.	Ratcliffe, Reece, Currie	100,0	1998	Luxembourg	61 000,0

If we study the experience of Finland, in this country family business can be found in every field. Their share varies depending on the size of each sector. A general analysis shows that family businesses dominate the accommodation and food service industries in Finland.

Figure 1. Analysis of the participation of family businesses in different sectors in Finland in 2022 [12]

Figure 1 analyzes the participation of family businesses in different sectors in Finland in 2022. In particular, we can see that large family businesses have the largest share in accommodation and food services (67%) and wholesale and retail trade (39%). In accommodation and food services, medium-sized family businesses also have the highest share (70%), while in construction it is second (56%). Accommodation and food services (85%) and construction (85%) were dominated by small family businesses.

CONCLUSION.

The following conclusions can be made by analyzing the international practice of family business.

1. The growth and survival of family companies in the conditions of intense competition depends on several aspects. First of all, it is necessary to organize effective corporate management in family business, and in this process it is necessary to take into account aspects different from corporate management organized in other forms of business. Secondly, there should be a unified

management to organize the directions of action of family members and to implement it correctly. Because this issue plays an important role in solving business problems and realizing goals.

2. Due to the fact that family business companies make up the majority of all companies in the world today, they create a large part of the average number of jobs and contribute to the global GDP, it can be concluded that family business is gaining importance around the world, and because of this, it is also important in our country. it is necessary to introduce effective organizational and practical mechanisms.

3. When studying the international experience of family business, it is necessary to pay attention to the organization of family business finance, directions for implementing family values and parallel effective business activities, aspects that should be taken into account when expanding family business and increasing its life span.

4. Based on international experience, it is important to study the family model of business organization and management and take into account the specific features of this model. Based on this, it is necessary to create conditions for family business representatives in our country to expand business and strengthen the position of family business in the economy.

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